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BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

THE SCENARIO OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY PROTECTION IN BRAZIL AND ITS EFFECTS ON CYBERSECURITY.

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Policy Statement

The cyber environment has been transforming into a crucial space in international politics today due to the high digitization of society in the mid-21st century. This new environment necessarily brings new threats, such as various cyber-attacks. One of the attacks that draws the most attention is those related to intellectual property theft (IP).

Brazil has a specific entity, the National Institute of Industrial Property (INPI), to address issues related to intellectual property. The Brazilian government has also established political and legislative strategies to reduce vulnerabilities and guide its actions in cyberspace. However, this documentary framework does not guarantee Brazil's maturity in cybersecurity, meaning that the country lacks adequate IP protection. In other words, vulnerabilities in cybersecurity contribute to IP theft in the national territory. This is coupled with reasonable IP production in Brazilian territory and considerable investments in the country's Research and Development (R&D).

Background

Brazil has been conjecturing and developing its cybersecurity strategies and policies since the first decade of the 21st century. This more institutionalized movement occurs mainly due to the relevance that the cyber sector has gained in recent years, where Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) are increasingly crucial for socio-economic development and national security. Thus, it is interpreted that formulating policies and guidelines in this area is part of a governance process involving cooperation arrangements among the multiple actors that make up the country's cybersecurity structure (Hurel; Lobato, 2018).

Not surprisingly, Brazil has published essential documents in the field, such as the National Cybersecurity Strategy (E-ciber) in 2020, the Brazilian Strategy for Digital Transformation (E-digital) in 2018, and more recently, the National Cybersecurity Policy (PNCIber) in 2023, among other documents. In addition, it has a governance structure on cybersecurity aspects and legislative apparatus on the subject to coordinate policy implementation, develop technical capabilities, and reduce cyber vulnerability.

One of the elements impacting the cybersecurity landscape and technological development in Brazil is Intellectual Property (IP). Possible causes for a low capacity to protect IP include weakened enforcement of regulations, difficulties in IP registration, and weak cyber capabilities. States with such characteristics are more vulnerable to IP theft. In this sense, as shown below, the existence of government documents and governance structure does not guarantee that the Brazilian cyber environment is secure.

Findings

One of the main challenges regarding Brazilian intellectual property is the difficulty in forming a qualified workforce in information technology and related areas. At the same time, reports from the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE) and the Institute of Applied Economic Research (IPEA) indicate that Brazil has high internet usage rates and a consolidated digital economy. Thus, it stands out that the country has become a more vulnerable target for intellectual property theft and one of the most targeted in cyber-attacks, given the low supply of qualified professionals and high utilization of the digital environment.

Another piece of highly relevant information pertains to the production of intellectual property in Brazil. The average growth rate in IP registrations in the country between 2013 and 2022 was about 11% per year, reaching approximately 438,000 applications in 2022, according to INPI statistics. Among all IP-intensive sectors in Brazil, there is an evident prevalence in the trademarks sector (31%), followed by industrial design (10.5%) and utility models (6.1%) (INPI, 2021). Meanwhile, the Ministry of Science, Technology, and Innovation (MCTI) estimates that Brazilian investment in Research and Development was about 1.14% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), reaching the mark of 20 billion dollars in 2020.

Additionally, it is presumed that a state's ability to face cyber-attacks and be resilient is linked to its capacity to legislate and implement policies and guidelines that encompass the cyber sector, as with intellectual property. In this case, public awareness of the issue is a factor that should be considered. However, according to the 2022 Inclusive Internet Index, Brazil ranks 44th out of 100 evaluated countries, indicating the level of digital education and policies for promoting digital education in

society. This means that the country needs help to include the entire Brazilian population in cyber-related matters, leading to a digital exclusion of some of the population.

This lack of population awareness is reflected in the Brazilian industry itself, given that a study conducted by CISCO in 2023, Cybersecurity Readiness Index, demonstrated that only 26% of Brazilian companies have the maturity and capability to deal with incidents and cybersecurity issues. Furthermore, according to the 2022 global Cybersecurity Workforce Study, an estimated 312,000 specialized professionals in the field of cybersecurity are lacking in Brazil. In other words, there is a shortage of skilled workforce to deal with cyber threats, indicating a scenario of vulnerability in the country.

Regarding Intellectual Property specifically, Brazil has an excellent organizational structure, represented primarily by INPI, the agency responsible for registering trademarks, patents, industrial design, and contracts to establish rules and IP rights in the country. INPI has various projects to promote research, technological innovation, and governance committees. However, Brazil needs help in the development and production of IP. According to the World Intellectual Property Organization, the country ranks 26th out of 193 countries concerning patent registration, with approximately 80.7% of registrations in 2021 being from foreign companies in the national territory.

This scenario reveals a specific weakness of Brazil in achieving robustness in its technological capabilities, as the development of national technology through its patents could be better. Consequently, cyber capabilities, in terms of infrastructure and digital systems in the country, are hindered by the lack of cutting-edge technological innovations, resulting in greater vulnerability and exposure to cyber-attacks and crimes.

Thus, it can be interpreted that even with a framework of regulation and promotion of cybersecurity, such as E-Ciber (2020), the General Data Protection Law (LGPD) of 2018, and the initiative of the Institutional Security Cabinet (GSI) that institutionalized the National Cyber Defense Policy in 2023, the practical implementation of guidelines for promoting technological development, research, digital education, and the formation of qualified workforce is still fragile. Looking at digital education, for example, according to a study by Kaspersky in 2020, about 62% of Brazilians do not know how to recognize fake news, indicating that Brazilian society is easily deceived in

the cyber realm and the public debate on cybersecurity is insufficient.

However, this context does not mean that the Brazilian government does not recognize the need for improvements in IP and cybersecurity. In 2021, the government published the National Intellectual Property Strategy, determining various actions and initiatives focused on training, institutional strengthening, legal security, and modernization of legal frameworks to insert Brazil into the global IP system. However, these actions still appear incipient, and Brazil's performance in having a large production of intellectual property and cyber robustness still needs to be improved.

Finally, it is worth noting Brazilian cooperation in technology with other actors, such as China and OECD countries. China has already established itself as Brazil's most significant economic partner. Chinese companies are gaining ground in producing electric and hybrid cars and operating 5G systems in Brazil (G1, 2021). Additionally, Brazil has various technological cooperation measures with OECD countries, such as in the aeronautical industry with Sweden (FAB, 2016) and in technology and innovation with the government and universities of North America (FIESC, 2018).

Recommendations

Given the outlined scenario, the most critical aspect for Brazil would be to build actions that simultaneously strengthen its technological capacity and reduce its dependence on other international actors in this field. In this regard, the Brazilian government should prioritize some specific actions. They are:

At the geopolitical strategic level:

- (i) work to reduce its technological dependence on major powers so that its vital security systems do not rely on technological resources manufactured in other countries. This requires budgetary investment and the development of a national technology and cybersecurity industry.
- (ii) understand the interests of all its international partners, especially China and the USA, regarding Brazil. Brazil should enhance its national intelligence system, especially in the face of cyber threats such as espionage and sabotage.

- (iii) being a developing country with limited budgetary resources for cutting-edge technology development, Brazil should emphasize the importance of international cooperation processes to promote Internet governance and prevent this resource from being used as a new weapon of war.
- (iv) Finally, Brazil must create a National Cyber Defense Strategy to defend the state's sovereignty against cyber threats. Although there is already a National Cybersecurity Strategy, Brazil needs to develop a document of this level for the defense sector.

At the creation and implementation of public policy level:

- (i) formulate robust public policies and strategies coordinating the state's cyber capabilities to prevent rapid and continuous cyber-attacks.
- (ii) establish a state agency dedicated to cybersecurity, centralizing and coordinating preventive measures and resilience strategies.
- (iii) promote awareness of cybersecurity among the general population, providing them with the necessary technological knowledge to safeguard themselves and effectively use emerging Technologies and;
- (iv) maintain an effective cybercrime fighting unit operating at various levels, covering cybersecurity and cyber defense.
- (v) develop and implement robust system recovery protocols to respond to cyber-attacks, ensuring that personnel are trained to react quickly and efficiently to restore affected systems

Conclusions

Finally, when considering Intellectual Property and cutting-edge technological resources, it becomes evident that the scenario of competition, espionage, and sabotage that already permeated the world before the advent of cyber technologies will continue to exist, but now with an increased capacity for action. The competition for the development and control of cutting-edge technologies is a reality on the global power chessboard; thus, the state that can pioneer the control of this productive and innovative chain in IP will be the global leader, capable of dictating the rules and paths that international politics will follow in the coming years.

China and the USA are by far the leading developers of Intellectual Property today. Still, at the same time, they are the ones most apprehensive about this competition and the rise of new players in this field. Therefore, Brazil must know this international competition and understand its role in this game. After this awareness, it is up to the Brazilian state to recognize that to protect itself and have any ability to act, it must heavily invest in developing cutting-edge technology that can translate into products with Intellectual Property. Simultaneously, it must create robust mechanisms to protect this sensitive area within the state.

Indeed, there seems to be only one path to materialize these recommendations that Brazil needs to enter the technological 21st century with some ability to act: a) understand that the state's investment in science, innovation, and technology must be substantial, enduring over time, and strategically planned; b) the state must massively invest in education to train a workforce in the technological field and to provide the population with knowledge on how to exist in the technological era and protect itself. Last, but not least, it is essential to c) build public-private partnerships so that the state encourages the private sector to produce increasingly advanced technology with Intellectual Property, creating an attractive business and technological development environment for both the domestic market and international players.

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